

Relation between different organic sources and N-mineralization in rice-mustard cropping sequence

Niladri Paul^{*a} and Dipankar Saha^b

^aDepartment of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, College of Agriculture, Agartala-799 210, Tripura, India

E-mail : nilupaul82@rediffmail.com

^bFormer, Department of Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Mohanpur-741 252, Nadia, West Bengal, India

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Abstract : The influence of organic matter vis-a-vis humic acids on soil nitrogen status and its availability and economic impact, during the cultivation of rice (Variety MTU 1010) followed by mustard (Variety B-9), was studied in the soil of Typic *Fluvaquent* situated in Old Alluvial Soil of West Bengal, India. The status of soil texture, bulk density, oxidizable organic carbon, pH, total nitrogen, available nitrogen and microbial biomass nitrogen were Sandy Clay Loam, 1.34 Mg m⁻³, 1.16 g 100 gm⁻¹, 6.34, 0.14 g 100 gm⁻¹, 231.36 kg ha⁻¹, 11.86 µg g⁻¹, respectively. The C : N ratio of the added FYM, Commercial and FYM extracted humic acid were 32.11, 32.61, 13.53 respectively. Along with recommended doses of fertilizers (N : P₂O₅ : K₂O :: 60 : 30 : 30 and 80 : 40 : 40) basal soil of paddy followed by mustard was treated with FYM (@ 10 and 5 t ha⁻¹), Commercial humic acid (@ 1.0, 0.5 kg ha⁻¹) and FYM extracted humic acid (@ 1.0, 0.5 kg ha⁻¹), respectively. The experiment was undertaken with 3 replications with plot size of (3×4 =) 12 sqm following the Randomized Block Design (RBD). Rhizosphere (0–15 cm) soil-plant samples were collected and analysed for total nitrogen, available nitrogen, microbial biomass nitrogen, plant uptake and their overall effect on yield of crops. At panicle initiation and branching stages of paddy and mustard highest content of total nitrogen was recorded which gradually decline towards harvesting stage. FYM extracted humic acid increased N-availability, MBN in soil which signified N-uptake within plants resulted significant yield of paddy. Residual effects from paddy irrespective of additional dose to mustard resulted similar yield effect on mustard and its biomass.

Keywords : FYM, humic acid, mineralizable nitrogen, MBN.

Introduction

The importance of organic matter in the soil is implicit in the definition of soil and also act as a direct part of soil fertility and nutrient source. Organic matter has a fundamental effect on soil physical properties and determines to a large degree of soils' physico-chemical characteristics. These properties are of great importance in controlling nutrient uptake, growth and development of the plant.

Nitrogen is an essential component of all amino acids. These amino acids are the building blocks of all proteins including the enzymes. These amino acids control virtually all biological processes. It is also essential for carbohydrate use within plants. Plants respond quickly to increased nitrogen availability as a result their leaves turn

deep green in colour. Nitrogen stimulates plant productivity also¹.

Humic acid is the major constituents of humic substances and it is the integral part of soil organic matter and one of the key component of terrestrial ecosystem. It may form an enzymatically active complex that can carry on reactions that are usually assigned to the metabolic activity of living organisms². Soil organic nitrogen is mainly present in the humic acid fractions where as only a small portion is present in fulvic acid fraction³. Humic acid fraction of humic substances contains 20 to 50% amino acid nitrogen⁴, 3 to 10% amino sugar nitrogen⁵, small amount of purine and pyrimidine⁶ and the rest unidentified. The amount of amino acid differs depending upon the origin of humic substances without only signifi-

cant relation between amino acid and soil type⁷.

Humic acid can be used as a supplement to chemical fertilizers based on the property of base exchange capacity and complexing ability required in soil⁸. Humic acid converts elements into forms suitable for plant assimilation⁹. It also contains many trace elements and various micronutrients in its structure and these are further complex to form chelates¹⁰ used for plant growth and development¹¹. Humic acid serves as a catalyst in promoting microbial activity in soil with a wide variety of enzymes – urease is the most abundant one¹². Addition of humic acid to soil increased the rate of adsorption of mineral ions on root surface and their penetration into the cells of plant tissues – correlated with biological availability of carbon pool¹³.

Different authors hypothesized that humic acid may be absorbed by plant roots and interact with root cells subsequently influence plant physiology and growth through respiratory activity via the quinone groups¹⁴. Humic acid also influences the metabolism of plant cells at different levels. It stimulates the uptake capacity of plant for phosphate, sodium, barium while that of calcium and zinc were unaffected¹⁵. Humic substances have been reputed to influence plant growth by increasing root vitality, nutrient uptake and increased chlorophyll synthesis¹⁶. Application of humic acid with recommended doses of fertilizers (NPK) increases the population of bacteria and fungi in soil as well as increasing the microbial biomass¹⁷ in soil.

Application of very high dose of humic acid is less effective on growth and yield of crops¹⁸. Application of low dose of humic acid increased bacterial and fungal

biota of soil and in their growth of maize plants¹⁹. Spraying of humic acid under field conditions improved sugar yield and nutrient concentrations in leaf blades and sheaths of sugar cane²⁰.

Continuous cultivation of irrigated rice results deterioration of soil health and gradual declination of yield. In an area of intensive cultivation, application of humic acid as nutrient source may also increase the productivity, reducing time of fallow or green manure of cultivation. Application of humic acid in a rice-blackgram cropping system in presence and absence of organic matter increases rice yield by 35%. The residual crop blackgram treated with humic acid proved its destination influence on grain and hauler yield²¹.

Addition of organic matter in improving soil fertility is well recognised²² but direct application of humic acid to soil and foliar as a source of nutrition and improving physical, chemical and biological properties of soils has not been studied in details.

Therefore, it is of practical significance to study the role of organic matter vis-a-vis humic acid on improvement of nutrient status as well as soil health in rice-mustard cropping system.

Materials and methods :

Two field experiments is conducted in succession at Sub-divisional Adoptive Research Farm, Kandi, Murshidabad, India having longitude and latitude of 23.95°N and 88.03°E respectively. The soil type is Typic *Fluvaquent*. Physical and chemical properties of the soil are presented in Table 1.

Humic acids, used as treatment materials in experi-

Table 1. Physical and chemical properties of the soils of experiment site

Sl. No.	Parameters	Unit	Field soil
1.	Soil Type		Typic <i>Fluvaquent</i>
2.	Soil texture		Sandy Clay Loam
	Mechanical analysis	Sand	%
		Silt	%
		Clay	%
3.	Bulk density	Mg m ⁻³	1.34
4.	Oxidizable Organic Carbon	g 100 gm ⁻¹	1.16
5.	pH	Soil : water = 1 : 2.5	6.34
6.	Total nitrogen	g 100 gm ⁻¹	0.14
7.	Available nitrogen	kg ha ⁻¹	231.36
8.	Microbial Biomass Nitrogen	µg g ⁻¹	11.86

ments, extracted from FYM by the process of ²³ and GR grade, commercial humic acid having 8% of ash was purchased from open market. The characteristics of FYM and humic acid purchased from market are placed in Table 2.

Rice (Variety MTU-1010) was cultivated with recommended doses of N, P₂O₅ and K₂O at 60, 30 and 30 kg ha⁻¹ in the form of urea, SSP and MOP, respectively to raise the rice crop with best management practices during kharif season. 50% of the total fertilizer nitrogen was applied as basal and the rest amount was applied in 2 split doses at tillering and flowering stages of rice. The plot size was 12 (3×4) sqm. The experiment was undertaken following the Randomized Block Design (RBD). Each treatment was replicated thrice. Mustard (B-9) was cultivated as relay crop with recommended dose of N, P₂O₅ and K₂O at 80, 40 and 40 kg ha⁻¹ in the form of urea, SSP and MOP, respectively.

The following treatments were adopted in the 1st and 2nd experiments in succession.

Treatments of the 1st experiment with rice :

T₁ = Soil + NPK at recommended dose

T₂ = T₁ + FYM at 1.0 tons ha⁻¹ at basal

T₃ = T₁ + Commercial humic acid at 1.0 kg ha⁻¹ at basal

T₄ = T₁ + Humic acid extracted from FYM at 1.0 kg ha⁻¹ at basal

Treatments of the 2nd experiment with mustard :

T₁' = Soil + NPK at recommended dose

T₂' = T₁' + FYM @ 5.0 t ha⁻¹

T₃' = T₁' + Commercial humic acid at 0.5 kg ha⁻¹ at basal

T₄' = T₁' + Humic acid extracted from FYM at 0.5 kg ha⁻¹ at basal

Collection and analysis of soil and plant samples :

Rhizosphere soil samples (0–15 cm) were collected from each of the respective treatment plot on tillering, panicle initiation, flowering and harvesting stages of rice followed by branching, flowering and harvesting stages of mustard. Total Nitrogen (TN) content of soil and plant samples was estimated with modern FOSS Kjeltec method following the procedure of modified Kjeldahl method as described in Jackson²⁶. Available nitrogen of soil was determined by alkaline potassium permanganate method²⁷. The microbial biomass nitrogen of the organic matter and humic acid treated soil samples were estimated by chloroform fumigated direct extraction (CFDE) protocol as established by Joergensen²⁸.

Statistical analysis :

Data of the experiments were analysed statistically for analysis of variance as well as critical difference were calculated at 5% level of significance to test the significance of means for the treatment difference following the procedure as described by Gomez and Gomez²⁹. (SEM = Standard Error of mean, CD = Critical Difference, CV = Coefficient of Variation).

Results and discussion

Effect of FYM @ 10 and 5 t ha⁻¹, commercial and

Table 2. Characteristics of FYM and humic acids of different sources

Sl. No.	Characteristics	FYM	Humic acid extracted from FYM	Commercial humic acid
1.	Oxidizable organic carbon (%)	32.56	29.77	43.36
2.	Total nitrogen (%)	1.014	2.2	1.29
3.	Viscosity (measured by Ubelhode viscometer)		133.1	139.0
4.	E ₄ /E ₆		3.193	3.41
5.	Functional group (measured by Dragunova ²⁴) (meq Ba)		6.803	6.803
6.	Ash free carboxylic group (Kononova ²⁵) (meq)		628.3	415.9

extracted humic acid @ 1.0 and 0.5 kg ha⁻¹ on paddy followed by mustard, respectively on the content of total nitrogen in soil were tabulated in Table 3. Commercial humic acid (CHA) with lowest C/N ratio (Table 2) act as readymade source of energy nitrogen to microbial community followed by extracted humic acid (EHA) (33 : 1). Aerobic bacteria use these as food source for microbial proliferation as compared to other microbial community³⁰. The proliferated bacteria had utilised applied commercial (CHA) and extracted humic acids (EHA) resulting significant influence of 36.7% and 33.4% on total nitrogen at tillering stage of rice in soil. After use of applied urea the rate of microbial degradation of FYM was going on resulting in gradual significant increase of TN at panicle initiation stage (17.3%) followed by tillering stage (15.6%) as compared to that of control³¹. Due to higher microbial activity the organic N present in soil was mineralized and utilized by plant³² showing a declining trend of TN towards harvesting stage³³.

During rabi season same field was cultivated with mustard having treatments of FYM, CHA and EHA @ 5.0 t, 0.5 and 0.5 kg ha⁻¹ respectively. Due to residual effect, contents of TN were increased in all mustard plots at branching stage. EHA treated plots showed declining

rate (8.8%) of TN where as FYM showed 9.6% increase as compared to control in soil. The rate of decline in the content of TN was narrower towards flowering stage resulted non-significant influence on the content of TN, irrespective of all treatments. This might be due to higher microbial degradation at FYM treated plots³⁴ and resistant power of humic acids towards microbial activity³⁵. At harvesting stage presence of EHA with greater dose resulted highest increase in the content of TN (16.2%) followed by FYM (13.5%) and CHA (3.0%) as compared to that of control.

Table 4 represents changes in available N in soil cropped with paddy followed by mustard with the treatments of FYM, CHA and EHA. The changes in the concentration of available nitrogen truly depend on the changes in TN and other physico-chemical and biological factors³⁶. Basal application of EHA and urea jointly increased the available nitrogen towards highest pick (66.7%) followed by CHA (40.0%) and FYM (33.3%) as compared to control in soil at tillering stage. Microbial mineralization was mainly responsible for raising amount of available nitrogen, which also affected the content of TN (Table 3) in soil. Along with the cultivation period, available nitrogen tended to decrease with increase in the age of crop.

Table 3. Changes in total N (g kg⁻¹) in soil treated with FYM and humic acid in rice-mustard cropping sequence

Treatments	Crop							
	Rice				Mustard			
	Days after transplanting of rice				Days after sowing of mustard			
	Tillering	Panicle initiation	Flowering	Harvesting	Treatments	Branching	Flowering	Harvesting
T ₁ = Soil + NPK at recommended dose	0.900	0.980	0.867	0.820	T ₁ ' = Soil + NPK at recommended dose	1.360	1.240	0.990
T ₂ = T ₁ + FYM at 10 tons ha ⁻¹ at basal	1.040	1.150	0.950	0.867	T ₂ ' = T ₁ ' + FYM at 5 tons ha ⁻¹ at basal	1.490	1.360	1.120
T ₃ = T ₁ + Commercial humic acid at 1.0 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	1.230	1.183	0.870	0.800	T ₃ ' = T ₁ ' + Commercial humic acid at 0.5 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	1.360	1.120	1.020
T ₄ = T ₁ + Humic acid extracted from FYM at 1.0 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	1.201	1.147	0.920	0.860	T ₄ ' = T ₁ ' + Humic acid extracted from FYM at 0.5 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	1.240	1.120	1.150
SEm(±)	0.0736	0.0368	0.0157	0.0173	SEm(±)	0.0223	0.0687	0.0329
CD(5%)	0.2546	0.1272	0.0544	0.0599(ns)	CD(5%)	0.0772	0.2379(ns)	0.1139
CV%	11.6642	5.7115	3.0204	3.5857	CV%	2.8346	9.8270	5.3232
SEm(±)		0.0386			SEm(±)		0.0531	
CD(5%)		0.1235			CD(5%)		0.1836	

Table 4. Changes in available N (kg ha⁻¹) in soil treated with FYM and humic acid in rice-mustard cropping sequence

Treatments	Crop							
	Rice				Mustard			
	Days after transplanting of rice				Days after sowing of mustard			
	Tillering	Panicle initiation	Flowering	Harvesting	Treatments	Branching	Flowering	Harvesting
T ₁ = Soil + NPK at recommended dose	188.16	175.62	163.07	100.36	T ₁ ' = Soil + NPK at recommended dose	216.10	170.90	150.53
T ₂ = T ₁ + FYM at 10 tons ha ⁻¹ at basal	250.88	263.43	225.79	137.99	T ₂ ' = T ₁ ' + FYM at 5 tons ha ⁻¹ at basal	280.98	275.96	200.70
T ₃ = T ₁ + Commercial humic acid at 1.0 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	263.42	238.34	176.62	100.35	T ₃ ' = T ₁ ' + Commercial humic acid at 0.5 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	376.35	225.79	210.74
T ₄ = T ₁ + Humic acid extracted from FYM at 1.0 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	313.62	263.42	230.14	137.98	T ₄ ' = T ₁ ' + Humic acid extracted from FYM at 0.5 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	386.35	300.05	225.79
SEm(±)	5.6542	9.6070	2.3524	4.8730	SEm(±)	2.1177	1.8205	2.7634
CD(5%)	19.5633	33.2395	8.1392	16.8603	CD(5%)	7.3269	6.2989	9.5613
CV%	3.8554	7.0747	2.0485	7.0825	CV%	1.1646	1.2967	2.4304
SEm(±)		10.1646			SEm(±)		20.6828	
CD(5%)		32.5133			CD(5%)		71.5610	

Judicious use of EHA (very low amount in comparison to FYM) by the microorganisms even by the plant roots³⁷ referred same amount of available nitrogen with FYM (50.0%) at PI stage where as highest content at flowering stage (41.1%) followed by FYM (38.5%) as compared with control. The microbial degradation of EHA was very slow due to the refractory nature of their chemical structures renders them more resistant to degradation by soil microorganisms³⁵ might be resulted equivalent level of available nitrogen at harvesting stage with FYM. During harvesting stage plant did not uplift N³⁸ but microbial mineralization continued to reach desired C/N ratio which resulted highest amount of available N (25.0%) in FYM treated plot in comparison to control in soil. CHA have low C/N ratio but the percent of N in that was very meagre and rapidly used by the microorganisms as well as plant roots. This might be the reason of decreasing rate of available nitrogen at flowering (8.3%) stage of paddy as compared to that of control. In this paddy – mustard cropping pattern mustard have a positive effect on residual available nitrogen present in soil³⁹. Along with this residual effect basal application of recommended chemical fertilizers raised the content of available nitro-

gen at control (Table 4). FYM, CHA and EHA acted as addendum on that and reflected significant increase in available nitrogen at branching. EHA in mustard resulted highest significant increase of 78.8% followed by EHA (74.2%) and FYM (30.0%) over control in soil. Mustard cultivation showed similar pattern in the content of available nitrogen as that of paddy (Table 4).

Microbial biomass nitrogen (MBN) is the microbial body protein and amino acids which was build during the microbial growth and utilization of substrates N by the microorganisms for their body build up⁴⁰. After death this body protein (Organic N) was mineralised and inorganic N was released – absorbed by the plant roots⁴⁰. Changes in the content of MBN also reflected the change in the content of available nitrogen in soil and their uses⁴¹. Table 5 represented this variation in the content of MBN at all stages of paddy and mustard cultivation. No definite trend was followed by paddy but mustard resulted inclining trend. Humic acid and FYM were the source of organic N used by the microbes after full utilization of inorganic N⁴² (Chandra, 2005) supplied at basal. Irrespective of treatments and cultivation period EHA resulted highest increase in the content of MBN followed

by CHA upto PI stage and FYM at flowering and harvesting stage of paddy as compared to that of control. This might be due to higher microbial inertness to humic acid³⁵ and gradual microbial mineralization of FYM³⁴. The amount of MBN present in soil was also depended on MBC and both of them always keep a stable ratio in soil⁴¹. Cultivation of mustard with earlier stated treatments resulted gradual increase in the content of MBN towards harvesting. At branching stage, use of EHA significantly established more than one fold increase in MBN followed by FYM (74.3%) and CHA (19.1%) over control in soil. Over the cultivation period EHA resulted highest increasing rate in the content of MBN followed by FYM and CHA in comparison to control in soil. This might be due to the residual effect of paddy on mustard³⁹ and microbial use of applied inorganic N in the form of urea.

The average N percent in plant dry weight and uptake by rice and mustard at different stages are presented in Tables 6 and 7. During the growth period the percent of plant N gradually declined from PI to harvesting stage whereas at harvesting, the combined N percentage of grain and straw established highest position over the growth

period. Positive increment during the growth period implied increase in dry weight towards harvesting stage. Uptake is the calculated figure of percent nutrient and average dry weight. Therefore, changes in nutrient percent and dry weight over the growth period affects nutrient uptake.

Over the cultivation period, application of EHA resulted highest increase in uptake of N by grain at harvesting stage (112.4%) followed by flowering (84.0%) stage. This might be due to movable characteristics of N within plant¹. Highest uptake of N in EHA treated system was followed by FYM and CHA, respectively at different growth stages of paddy. This result implied the power of microbial mineralization for nutrient availability⁴³ in soil. Basal application of humic acid with justified dose⁴⁴ may bring some close contact between humic acid and plant root which enabled roots to intake fractions of humic acid resulted increase in metabolic activity within plant body⁴⁵. Secretion of metabolically created products through root exudation, resulted increase in N uptake within plant body in exchange reaction⁴⁵ resulted highest increase in dry weight in plant, nutrient percentage in grain and all along uptake of nitrogen.

Table 5. Changes in Microbial Biomass Nitrogen ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) in soil treated with FYM and humic acid in rice-mustard cropping sequence

Treatments	Crop							
	Rice				Mustard			
	Days after transplanting of rice				Days after sowing of mustard			
	Tillering	Panicle initiation	Flowering	Harvesting		Branching	Flowering	Harvesting
T ₁ = Soil + NPK at recommended dose	10.41	14.92	18.97	15.60	T ₁ ' = Soil + NPK at recommended dose	16.02	18.70	15.03
T ₂ = T ₁ + FYM at 10 tons ha ⁻¹ at basal	15.23	17.22	25.22	23.12	T ₂ ' = T ₁ ' + FYM at 5 tons ha ⁻¹ at basal	27.93	32.76	30.95
T ₃ = T ₁ + Commercial humic acid at 1.0 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	17.75	26.66	24.77	16.35	T ₃ ' = T ₁ ' + Commercial humic acid at 0.5 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	19.08	25.43	23.26
T ₄ = T ₁ + Humic acid extracted from FYM at 1.0 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	18.11	27.68	25.89	25.38	T ₄ ' = T ₁ ' + Humic acid extracted from FYM at 0.5 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	39.13	49.10	44.94
SEm(±)	1.3849	0.8193	1.1547	1.1538	SEm(±)	2.8869	4.1118	2.6264
CD(5%)	4.7917	2.8346	3.9952	3.9921	CD(5%)	9.9883	14.2267	9.0871
CV%	15.6015	6.5634	8.4344	9.9365	CV%	19.5779	22.6111	15.9364
SEm(±)			1.5385		SEm(±)		1.0307	
CD(5%)			4.9212		CD(5%)		3.5662	

Table 6. Changes in N content, dry matter yield and N-uptake at different growth stages of rice grown in soil treated with FYM vis-à-vis humic acid in a rice-mustard cropping sequence

Treatments	Harvesting (2011-12) Rice											
	Panicle initiation			Flowering			Straw			Grain		
	N%	Dry matter (kg ha ⁻¹)	Uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	N%	Dry matter (kg ha ⁻¹)	Uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	N%	Dry matter (kg ha ⁻¹)	Uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	N%	Dry matter (kg ha ⁻¹)	Uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)
T ₁ = Soil + NPK at recommended dose	1.87	216.87	4.06	1.26	445.78	5.62	0.72	4612.50	33.21	1.61	3123.00	50.30
T ₂ = T ₁ + FYM at 10 tons ha ⁻¹ at basal	2.20	251.41	5.53	1.90	516.43	9.81	0.92	5593.50	51.46	1.99	3375.00	67.13
T ₃ = T ₁ + Commercial humic acid at 1.0 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	2.09	250.78	5.24	1.75	515.15	9.02	0.76	5283.00	40.18	2.61	3663.00	95.59
T ₄ = T ₁ + Humic acid extracted from FYM at 1.0 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	2.12	289.09	6.13	1.87	552.74	10.34	0.86	5850.00	50.30	2.85	3748.50	106.85
SEm(±)	0.0602	0.1806	0.1636	0.0548	0.2858	0.2851	0.0189	28.1073	1.0897	0.0972	17.5016	3.3311
CD(5%)	0.2082	0.6250	0.5660	0.1895	0.9887	0.9865	0.0652	97.2494	3.7703	0.3364	60.5543	11.5255
CV%	5.0359	0.1241	5.4083	5.5970	0.0975	5.6793	4.0073	0.9126	4.3103	7.4348	0.8717	7.2152

In Table 7, application of the same treatments (variable dose) results increase in N percent, dry weight and nutrient uptake with in plant body. With the same reason

highest uptake was recorded in seeds of harvesting stage (128.7%) by EHA, followed by FYM (114.4%) as compared to that of control in plant. Mustard cultivation was

Table 7. Changes in N content, dry matter yield and N-uptake at different growth stages of mustard grown in soil treated with FYM vis-à-vis humic acid in a rice-mustard cropping sequence

Treatments (Mustard)	Mustard (2011-12)											
	Branching			Flowering			Stover			Seed		
	N%	Dry matter (kg ha ⁻¹)	Uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	N%	Dry matter (kg ha ⁻¹)	Uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	N%	Dry matter (kg ha ⁻¹)	Uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	N%	Dry matter (kg ha ⁻¹)	Uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)
T ₁ ' = Soil + NPK at recommended dose	1.06	498.00	5.28	1.36	996.00	13.54	0.37	3036.56	11.22	2.11	915.08	19.32
T ₂ ' = T ₁ ' + FYM at 5.0 tons ha ⁻¹ at basal	1.37	531.20	7.28	1.73	1987.85	34.33	0.50	3805.97	19.01	2.48	1673.28	41.43
T ₃ ' = T ₁ ' + Commercial humic acid at 0.5 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	1.30	539.50	7.00	1.73	1817.70	31.45	0.74	2722.82	20.15	2.39	1150.38	27.49
T ₄ ' = T ₁ ' + Humic acid extracted from FYM at 0.5 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	1.49	560.25	8.34	1.94	1846.75	35.82	0.87	3114.99	27.09	2.60	1701.66	44.19
SEm(±)	0.0740	5.2854	0.4331	0.0634	33.2148	0.6377	0.0350	22.2785	1.0303	0.0222	24.7570	0.9314
CD(5%)	0.2561	18.2872	1.4985	0.2194	114.9210	2.2062	0.1210	77.0823	3.5648	0.0769	85.6576	3.2224
CV%	9.8288	1.7200	10.7529	6.4999	3.4613	3.8367	9.7666	1.2172	9.2128	1.6098	3.1527	4.8728

Table 8. Yield of paddy and mustard grown under different treatment combinations

Treatments	Paddy yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Treatments	Mustard yield (q ha ⁻¹)	
	Grain	Straw		Stover	Seed
T ₁ = Soil + NPK at recommended dose	3.470	5.125	T ₁ ' = Soil + NPK at recommended dose	35.83	10.00
T ₂ = T ₁ + FYM at 10 tons ha ⁻¹ at basal	3.750	6.215	T ₂ ' = T ₁ ' + FYM at 5.0 tons ha ⁻¹ at basal	42.50	11.25
T ₃ = T ₁ + Commercial humic acid at 1.0 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	4.070	5.870	T ₃ ' = T ₁ ' + Commercial humic acid at 0.5 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	31.66	10.66
T ₄ = T ₁ + Humic acid extracted from FYM at 1.0 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	4.165	6.500	T ₄ ' = T ₁ ' + Humic acid extracted from FYM at 0.5 kg ha ⁻¹ at basal	41.67	11.33
SEm(±)	0.0738	0.0504	SEm(±)	3.879	0.316
CD(5%)	0.2552	0.1743	CD(5%)	13.422(ns)	1.0950
CV%	3.3067	1.4723	CV%	17.721	5.071

followed by paddy and so the residual effect of FYM, applied at kharif season along with fresh application at basal of mustard resulted 2nd highest increase in N uptake of mustard during the whole cultivation period.

Variation in grain and straw yield of paddy along with stover and seed yield of mustard was tabulated in Table 8. Highest increase in grain (20.03%) and straw (28.83%) yield were recorded with EHA followed by CHA – 17.29% and 14.54%, respectively. In mustard highest production of stover (18.62%) and seed (13.30%) was observed with application of FYM and EHA respectively as compared to that of control in plant. This result in mustard might be due to residual effect of paddy³⁹ along with added application of FYM, CHA and EHA.

Conclusion

Application of EHA at basal collectively with recommended doses of fertilizers increase N-availability, content of MBN in soil which signifies N-uptake within plants resulted significant yield of paddy. Residual effect of paddy along with additional dose of EHA to mustard resulted highest significant quantitative yield.

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